

Impact of reactor antineutrinos on the neutrino floor in low-mass WIMP searches

(based on: [arxiv:2511.09217](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.09217))

Sudipta Das*, Varchaswi KS Kashyap,
Bedangadas Mohanty

NISER, India

Direct WIMP Search

- ◆ Weakly Interacting Massive Particle (WIMP): well motivated Dark Matter (DM) candidate.
- ◆ Galactic WIMPs **elastically scatter off detector nuclei**
- ◆ Signals: **low-energy nuclear recoils**
- ◆ Underground operation suppresses environmental backgrounds
- ◆ Experimental sensitivity is primarily driven by
 - ◆ Energy threshold of detectors
 - ◆ Target mass or exposure

Neutrino Floor: The Big Picture

WIMP Interaction

Neutrino Interaction

- ◆ Neutrinos interact via **coherent elastic neutrino–nucleus scattering (CE ν NS)**
- ◆ Produces indistinguishable nuclear recoils
- ◆ Can't be shielded \rightarrow irreducible background
- ◆ Limits WIMP discovery potential.
- ◆ **Forms “neutrino fog”**

Neutrino Floor: The Big Picture

← Threshold

elastic neutrino-
 clear recoils
 background
 l.

Neutrino Floor: The Big Picture

WIMP Interaction

Exposure

elastic neutrino-
clear recoils
background

Key question: How & Where nearby nuclear reactors modifies the neutrino floor?

← Threshold

Spectral Degeneracy: WIMPs vs CE ν NS

✓ **WIMP–nucleus elastic scattering:**

Signal

$$\frac{dR}{dE_R} = \frac{N_A}{A} \frac{\sigma_N}{2\mu_N^2} F^2(E_R) \times \frac{\rho_0}{M_\chi} \int_{v_{\min}}^{v_{\text{esc}}} \frac{f(\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v}_E)}{v} d^3v$$

Rate per unit mass

Cross-section & Detector effect

Flux

✓ **Neutrino–nucleus elastic scattering:**

Background

$$\frac{dR}{dE_R} = \frac{N_A}{A} \sum_j \int_{E_\nu^{\min}(E_R)}^{E_\nu^{\max,j}} \frac{d\sigma(E_\nu, E_R)}{dE_R} dE_\nu \times \phi_j(E_\nu)$$

◆ **Detector Effects in the Measured Signal (SuperCDMS-like Ge HV detector)**

- ◆ Nuclear recoils exhibit reduced ionisation yield (**quenching**)
- ◆ Lindhard quenching model with $k = 0.162$ applied
- ◆ Minimal impact on the neutrino floor, as both WIMPs and CE ν NS produce nuclear recoils

Spectral Degeneracy: WIMPs vs CE ν NS

- Recoil primarily spectrum depends on: WIMP mass / neutrino energy

◆ Natural sources:

- ◆ Solar neutrinos
- ◆ Atmospheric neutrinos
- ◆ Geo-neutrinos
- ◆ Diffuse supernova neutrinos (DSNB)
- ◆ 6 GeV/c² WIMP signal closely mimics ⁸B solar CE ν NS spectrum.

◆ Man-made sources:

- ◆ Reactor anti-neutrinos

CE ν NS from Reactor Antineutrinos

- ◆ Nuclear reactor: Intense, man-made $\bar{\nu}_e$ source
- ◆ CONUS+ reported first evidence of CE ν NS measurement from reactor anti-neutrinos at 3.7σ CL [1].
- ◆ We validated our CE ν NS rate calculations against CONUS+ measurement.

CONUS+ KKL-Reactor

Reactor power	3.6 GW _{th}
Fission fraction	²³⁵ U: 0.53, ²³⁹ Pu:0.32, ²³⁸ U: 0.08, ²⁴¹ Pu:0.07
Integrated Flux	~15 x 10 ¹² cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ @ 20.7m

[1] [Nature](#) volume 643, pages 1229–1233 (2025)

CE $\bar{\nu}$ NS from Reactor Antineutrinos

- ◆ Anti-neutrino flux scales as $1/L^2$ with distance
- ◆ Start to dominate at low recoil energies below ~ 10 km
- ◆ Strong spectral overlap with: Low-mass WIMPs (~ 3 GeV/ c^2)

Opacity-Based Neutrino Floor: Definition

$$\mathcal{L}(\sigma_{\chi-n}, \Phi) = \prod_{i=1}^{N_{\text{bins}}} P \left(N_i^{\text{obs}} \mid N_i^{\chi} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\nu}} N_i^{\nu(j)}(\Phi_j) \right) \times \prod_{j=1}^{n_{\nu}} G(\Phi_j)$$

Observed count

WIMP count

CEvNS count

Flux uncertainty as
Gaussian constrain

a) Binned likelihood

◆ Binned Profile Likelihood Ratio methods for discovery sensitivity

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\mathcal{L}(\sigma_{\chi-n} = 0, \{\hat{\phi}\})}{\mathcal{L}(\hat{\sigma}_{\chi-n}, \{\hat{\phi}\})}$$

b) Likelihood ratio

$$q_0 = \begin{cases} -2 \ln(\lambda_0), & \hat{\sigma}_{\chi} > 0 \\ 0, & \hat{\sigma}_{\chi} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

c) Test statistics

◆ $\sigma_{\chi-n}^{Z=3}$: **Cross-section** that results WIMPs detection at 3σ CL in presence of CEvNS background.

Find $\sigma_{\chi-n}^{Z=3}$, yielding
 Z (Significance) = $\sqrt{q_0} = 3$

Opacity-Based Neutrino Floor: Definition

- ◆ Opacity: $n = - \left(\frac{d \ln \sigma_{\chi-n}^{Z=3}}{d \ln N_\nu} \right)^{-1}$
- ◆ **Neutrino floor: $n = 2$**
- ◆ Boundary where systematic uncertainty starts to dominate over statistical uncertainty.

Impact of reactor $\bar{\nu}$ on the Neutrino Floor

- ◆ Reactor antineutrinos introduce a **new low-mass neutrino fog**
- ◆ Strongest impact at: $m_\chi \sim 2.5\text{--}3$ GeV
- ◆ Varies strongly with reactor-detector distances $\sigma/\sigma_{\text{baseline}}$

Reactor-Detector distance (km)	$\sigma/\sigma_{\text{baseline}}$
1	326.15
5	12.77
10	3.68
50	1.03
100	1

Implications for Future Dark Matter Experiments

- ◆ Reactor antineutrinos must be included in sensitivity projections for future experiments
- ◆ Low-mass DM searches require:
 - ◆ Careful site selection
 - ◆ Distances >100 km from GW-scale reactors
 - ◆ Directional detection to mitigate reactor-induced neutrino fog

Summary

- ◆ **Reactor antineutrinos** can constitute a critical background for **2-3 GeV/c² WIMP** searches
- ◆ The impact of reactor antineutrinos on the neutrino floor is **strongly site dependent**
 - ◆ **Up to two orders of magnitude sensitivity degradation below 10 km**
 - ◆ **Negligible impact beyond ~100 km**
- ◆ Careful site selection is essential for future low-mass dark matter experiments.

Thank you :-)

Backup

CE ν NS: Coherent Elastic Neutrino Nucleus Scattering

- ◆ Flavour-independent process. $\nu + N(A,Z) \rightarrow \nu + N(A,Z)$
- ◆ Low momentum transfer: $|q| \leq \frac{1}{R_N} \rightarrow$ Nucleon amplitudes sum up coherently.
- ◆ Larger cross-section compared to other Neutrino-SM interactions.

$\Rightarrow \frac{d\sigma}{dE_R} \propto N^2$, where, $N =$ target nucleus neutron number
 $E_R =$ Nuclear recoil energy

Elastic coherent (CE ν NS) [1]
 $\lambda_{Z^0} \gtrsim 2R$

[1] EPL 143 34001
 [2] Science 357, 1123–1126 (2017)

Neutrino flux normalisation uncertainty

Neutrino Sources	Systematic Uncertainty
Solar <ul style="list-style-type: none">• PP• Pep• hep• ^7Be• ^7Be• ^8B• ^{13}N• ^{15}O• ^{17}F	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 0.6%• 1%• 30%• 6%• 6%• 16%• 15%• 17%• 20%
DSNB	50%
Atmospheric	25%
Geo <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ^{40}K• ^{238}U• ^{232}Th	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 6%• 30%• 30%
Reactor	8%

[1] Phys. Rev. D 102, 063024 (2020)

[2] Phys. Rev. D 99, 093009 (2019)

Reactor anti-neutrino spectrum shape variation

Reactor parameters

Reactor power

3.6 GW_{th}

Fission fraction 1

²³⁵U: 0.53, ²³⁹Pu:0.32, ²³⁸U: 0.08, ²⁴¹Pu:0.07

Fission fraction 2

²³⁵U: 0.991, ²³⁹Pu:<0.01, ²³⁸U:<0.01,
²⁴¹Pu:<0.01

◆ Effect from variation of reactor anti-neutrino spectral shape from various fission fraction is limited to 10%

Reactor anti-neutrino flux uncertainty variation

Reactor parameters	
Reactor power	3.6 GW _{th}
Flux uncertainty 1	8%
Flux uncertainty 2	0.8%

- ◆ Significant improvement on sensitivity with 10 times reduction in systematic uncertainty at **1 km**.
- ◆ Negligible change for 10 km distance.

- ◆ Discovery limit based neutrino floor
- ◆ $Z \geq 3$ at 90% power

Detector configuration

Detector configuration	
Material	SuperCDMS like Ge HV ultra low threshold detector
Lindhard quenching	$k=0.162 \pm 0.004$
Assumed threshold & Exposure	1 eV _{nr} & up to 10 ¹⁰ ton-year.

- ◆ The threshold and high-exposure combination used is idealised and is used to isolate the physics of WIMP–neutrino spectral degeneracy
- ◆ No current or near-future experiment represent this combined configuration
- ◆ Neutrino floor varies with target materials. We focused on Ge detector only.

Multiple nearby reactor configurations

- ◆ Multiple reactor sites near DM search experiments are possible.
- ◆ The combined neutrino floor is effectively equivalent to that produced by a single reactor located at an effective distance.